

Repetition rate optimized 2 μm gain-switched diode pumped MIR supercontinuum

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Mid-infrared supercontinuum (SC) sources can benefit from low-cost pumps with center wavelength longer than the zero-dispersion wavelength of fluoride fibers (~ 1600 nm). This makes thulium-doped lasers an attractive technology, but their relative intensity noise (RIN) is typically not characterized. Furthermore, is low pump noise even a requirement for SC applications? With focus on low cost, we have developed a three-stage amplified 1946 nm gain-switched diode (GSD) demonstrating 12% RIN and flexible repetition rate control, which crucially allows the user to optimize SC performance specific to the application. We demonstrate a maximum -10 dB bandwidth of 1873–3986 nm at 2 MHz and a minimum RIN of 6.1% at 1900 nm, 10.4% at 2300 nm, and 16.6% at 3250 nm at 1 MHz. We define a figure of merit for operation between the 3000 and 3500 nm region and demonstrate that it is maximized at 3 MHz, showcasing the power of this control in optimizing specific performance metrics. This performance is compared with a SC spanning 1900–3796 nm, pumped by an amplified thulium-doped mode-locked fiber laser operating at 5.8 MHz with $< 0.11\%$ RIN. Despite the vastly superior pump noise, comparative SC RIN values of 2.0% at 1900 nm, 9.5% at 2300 nm, and 8.5% at 3250 nm were obtained, indicating that the modulational instability driven SC generation process dominates noise performance, thereby reducing the need for low pump noise. © 2024 Optica Publishing Group under the terms of the [Optica Open Access Publishing Agreement](https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAB.539907)

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mid-infrared (MIR) supercontinuum (SC) sources are desirable for applications requiring broad bandwidth and high brightness, including spectroscopy [1], microscopy [2], and imaging [3]. They are attractive for optical coherence tomography (OCT) of non-biological materials, where the MIR wavelengths permit deeper sample penetration compared to near-infrared sources, and the broad bandwidth ensures high axial resolution can be maintained [4]. To maximize the application signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) one would ideally maximize power spectral density and minimize the impact of pulse energy fluctuations. The deleterious impact of these fluctuations can be reduced by operating with a low pulse-to-pulse relative intensity noise (RIN), and a high pulse repetition rate (PRR), which allows greater signal averaging for a fixed integration time for spectrometer-based applications. This was demonstrated with improved OCT image quality when commercial modulation instability (MI)-based supercontinuum sources at 80 MHz and 320 MHz were compared [5]. In this work we conduct a comprehensive investigation into the effect of pump PRR on MIR SC RIN.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Gain-Switched Diode Pump

To initiate MIR supercontinuum generation (SCG), we pumped a ZrF₄-BaF₂-LaF₃-AlF₃-NaF (ZBLAN) fiber with ps pulses from an amplified 1946 nm gain-switched diode (GSD). Efficient SCG can arise from MI and soliton dynamics when pumping in the anomalous dispersion regime [6]. Figure 1 shows the measured dispersion profile for the 7.2 μm core diameter ZBLAN fiber (FiberLabs Inc.) used in this work, obtained using the interferometric technique outlined in [7]. With a first zero dispersion wavelength at 1530 nm, and a second at 4475 nm, we see that pumping at 1946 nm is sensible for efficient SCG. Pumping directly at longer wavelengths offers simplicity and efficiency benefits over the commonly employed technique of red-shifting a 1550 nm source using a fiber cascade [8–10].

To minimize cost and complexity the GSD pump source (Fig. 2) employed a three-stage amplifier design similar to that in [11], negating the need for a fourth amplification stage and electro-optic modulator for amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) removal as in [12]. This architecture offers attractive

Fig. 1. Measured dispersion profile for 7.2 μm core diameter ZBLAN fiber.

features including robustness, fully fiberized design, and simple control of the PRR (as in [13]), providing a key advantage over mode-locked systems. In this work, we operated in the picosecond regime and investigated PRRs between 1 and 10 MHz.

The pump source is based on a 1946 nm laser diode (Eblana Photonics, red in Fig. 2) gain-switched by quasi-square electrical pulses with 330 ps width and 5 V amplitude sent from a waveform generator (Active Technologies). The PRR was controlled by varying the frequency of the electrical pulses. The 1946 nm output was confined to a single longitudinal mode, with ~ 60 GHz linewidth, and low pulse energy, $< \text{pJ}$; thus significant amplification was required prior to SCG. This was achieved in a three-stage thulium-doped fiber (TDF) amplifier, consisting of two core-pumped pre-amplifier stages and one cladding-pumped power amplifier stage. The pre-amplifier pump was constructed from a fiberized 1550 nm laser diode (Thorlabs, Inc., green in Fig. 2) amplified in 6 m of 10 μm core diameter erbium/ytterbium-doped fiber (Exail) pumped by a 915 nm diode (nLight, blue in Fig. 2). The 1550 nm amplifier output was sent through an isolator and subsequently split using a 50:50 fiber coupler, with each arm incorporating a wavelength division multiplexer, allowing 550 mW of 1550 nm pump light to co-propagate with the 1946 nm signal through each

pre-amplifier. The first pre-amplifier (Tm1) consisted of 10 m of 5 μm core diameter TDF (OFS). Due to the low pulse energies and duty cycle, the continuous 1550 nm pump generated significant amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) in the pre-amplifier stages, limiting the achievable gain. Out-of-band ASE was removed after each pre-amplifier using a combined circulator and fiber Bragg grating (Exail) with a reflection bandwidth of 1 nm at 1946 nm. The second pre-amplifier (Tm2) consisted of 6 m of 9 μm core diameter TDF (Coherent, Inc.), while the final power amplifier (Tm3) employed 1.5 m of 10 μm core diameter double-clad TDF (Exail) pumped by a 793 nm diode (nLight, purple in Fig. 2). For the following pump source characterization the output of Tm3 was cleaved at $\sim 8^\circ$ to prevent back-reflections.

Figure 3 shows 1946 nm Tm3 output power for each PRR as a function of launched 793 nm power up to 8.9 W (5.9 W absorbed). The maximum output power ranged from 1.24 W at 2 MHz, to 1.58 W at 10 MHz, with a maximum gain of 66 dB at 1 MHz. However, ASE could constitute a portion of the output power, and may explain the slight decrease between 1 and 2 MHz, as increasing the PRR allows less opportunity for ASE to build up between pulses. All further measurements were taken at the maximum output power (using 8.9 W of 793 nm pump power). The pulse duration exceeded the speed of our 4 GHz oscilloscope (HDO9404, Teledyne Lecroy); therefore we utilized autocorrelation (AC) to estimate pulse duration. AC measurements across the tested repetition rates (pulseCheck SM, APE GmbH) suggest a non-idealized pulse shape, with broad shoulders around a central peak, as exemplified at 1 MHz (Fig. 3, inset). A sech^2 and Gaussian fit corresponding to a retrieved pulse full width half maximum (FWHM) of 15 ps provide a reasonable fit to the central peak but fit poorly to the shoulder region. We lack information on the initial pulse shape from the diode, or potential reshaping that occurs in the subsequent fiber arrangement. Since autocorrelation inherently requires confident knowledge of the pulse shape, these results should rather be taken as indicative values of the pulse duration. The AC FWHM generally increases with PRR from a value of

Fig. 2. 1946 nm pump source and SCG stage. Arrows indicate wavelength and direction of diode radiation. WFG = waveform generator, ISO = isolator, CIR + FBG = circulator + fiber Bragg grating.

Fig. 3. Tm3 1946 nm output versus 793 nm pump power for selected PRR. Inset: AC trace (blue), sech^2 -fit (red), and Gaussian-fit (green) at 1 MHz.

21.3 ps at 1 MHz to 35.2 ps at 10 MHz, indicating pulse durations below 35.2 ps. Finally, the RIN of the pump source was measured following the protocol outlined in [14]. The method is based on a photodiode (PDAVJ10, Thorlabs, Inc.) connected to an oscilloscope to capture the pulse train. The RIN varied very little with PRR, with values falling between 11.6–12.5 % [Fig. 6(a), inset].

B. Supercontinuum Generation

Following pump characterization, Tm3 was flat-cleaved and spliced to an isolator with SM1950 pigtailed (Precision Micro-Optics Inc.). This splice was affixed to the optical table with graphite tape, which facilitated removal of unabsorbed pump from the cladding. The length of SM1950 fiber before the isolator was kept short (~ 20 cm), to minimize pulse break-up and spectral broadening, which increases isolator loss. The length of SM1950 fiber after the isolator was used to initiate pulse break-up through MI, generating longer wavelength femtosecond solitons to facilitate efficient SCG in the subsequent ZBLAN fiber (Fig. 2) [9]. The length was optimized (at 1 MHz) to ~ 40 cm by maximizing power generated above $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ in the subsequent ZBLAN fiber. Note that the loss of SM1950 output was butt-coupled to the FC/PC connectorized input of 4 m of ZBLAN fiber. The output end of the ZBLAN fiber was terminated with a FC/APC connector to minimize feedback.

Figure 4 shows the dependence on PRR of three efficiencies. First, the transmission efficiency from Tm3 through the isolator and SM1950 pigtailed (blue) shows an increase from 52% at 1 MHz, to 76% at 10 MHz. This increase could be attributed to the higher peak powers at lower PRRs, which initiate more broadening in the SM1950 fiber, leading to increased loss in the isolator, which is optimized for 1950 nm. Second, the transmission from the output SM1950 pigtail through the ZBLAN fiber (green) is more constant, with values ranging from 60.2% at 2 MHz, to 66.4% at 10 MHz. The slight increase could be attributed to reduced spectral broadening at higher PRRs [Fig. 5(b)], and thus less light at the $4.0 \mu\text{m}$ ZBLAN loss edge. Finally, the ratio of output power at wavelengths above $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ to the total ZBLAN output power (red) peaks at 42.1% at 2 MHz, with a decrease for higher PRRs. Interestingly, the

Fig. 4. Efficiencies: Tm3 through the isolator + SM1950 fiber (blue), SM1950 fiber through ZBLAN fiber (green), and ratio of ZBLAN fiber output power above $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ to total output power (red).

Fig. 5. GSD pumped SCG from (a) SM1950, and (b) ZBLAN, with mode-locked (ML) pumped spectrum; labelled spectral regions R1, R2, and R3.

maximum was achieved at 2 MHz, despite the optimization of the SC bandwidth at 1 MHz. This could be explained by a trade-off between increased loss through the isolator and higher ASE due to a reduced duty cycle at lower PRRs, and reduced spectral broadening in the ZBLAN fiber due to lower peak power for higher PRRs. Output spectra were measured from the SM1950 [Fig. 5(a)] and ZBLAN fibers [Fig. 5(b)] using a grating-based spectrometer (S3, Miriad Technologies Ltd). The spectral bandwidth out the ZBLAN was defined as the -10 dB width from the SC maxima (excluding the pump region). The broadest spectrum out of the ZBLAN fiber was achieved at 2 MHz, with a bandwidth of 1873–3986 nm.

C. Relative Intensity Noise Characterization

The RIN was measured at three spectral regions using band-pass filters at 1900 ± 100 nm (R1), 2300 ± 25 nm (R2), and 3250 ± 250 nm (R3). It is observed that the SM1950 fiber RIN increases slightly with PRR for R1, and more dramatically for R2 [Fig. 6(a)], since this region is located towards the inherently noisier edge of the spectrum. At 4 MHz, only the weak and noisy IR edge of the spectrum overlaps with R2, such that the RIN becomes less meaningful, and at higher PRRs the peak power is too low to provide sufficient broadening. For the ZBLAN output [Fig. 6(b)], the RIN at R1 is fairly constant with values ranging between 5.6 and 6.2%, which is approximately half that of the pump. However, as expected the RIN increases with PRR in the other two regions, with an increase from 10.4–16.8% at R2 and an increase from 16.6–35% at R3 for 1–5 MHz. These values are comparable, although higher than the 5–10% values measured at 200 kHz in [15], which utilized a nanosecond 1550 nm pump in a cascaded fiber architecture. For PRRs greater than 3 MHz the power at R3 significantly decreases, consistent with the large increase in RIN to 83.8% at 10 MHz. The evolution of RIN at different spectral positions is a complicated process that is influenced by multiple factors including pulse duration, peak power, and position within the fiber system. A number of solitons are generated through the MI process, with this number generally decreasing with PRR. These generated solitons can undergo collisions, whereby a greater number of solitons, and consequently a greater number of soliton collisions, can lead to a larger red shift and ultimately a larger spectral bandwidth [16].

D. Figure of Merit

We have shown that 1 MHz is optimal for minimizing RIN and 2 MHz is optimal for maximizing bandwidth. However, to select the optimal conditions for maximizing SNR in a specific application, one needs to consider the PSD, RIN, and PRR. In fact, it may be preferable to operate with a higher RIN, if the benefit of operating at a higher PRR outweighs the higher RIN. This is because the SNR within a fixed integration time can increase with the square root of the number of averaged spectra (PRR), for non-correlated pulses in the absence of other dominating noise sources [17]. To demonstrate the power of this optimization, we define a figure of merit for time-averaged applications (FOM), which combines PSD, RIN, and PRR:

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{\text{PSD} \sqrt{\text{PRR}}}{\text{RIN}}. \quad (1)$$

For example, if we consider a spectrometer-based application, such as MIR OCT imaging, and want to optimize performance in the 3000–3500 nm spectral region, i.e., R3, we can use the FOM to determine the optimum PRR. This data (Fig. 7) shows that in this spectral region a peak FOM of $0.93 \text{ mW} \cdot \text{MHz}^{0.5} / \text{nm}$ is achieved at 3 MHz, despite minimum RIN and maximum bandwidth being achieved at 1 MHz and 2 MHz, respectively. This non-trivial conclusion results from the comprehensive spectral and RIN characterization, and positions a potential user optimally for applications.

Fig. 6. (a) Spectrally resolved RIN of SM1950 output for regions R1 and R2, with GSD and ML pump RIN (inset) and (b) spectrally resolved RIN of ZBLAN output for regions R1, R2, and R3 from both GSD and ML pumps.

Fig. 7. FOM for all PRRs for spectral region R3.

E. Comparison with Mode-Locked Pump

Another intuitive approach to reducing the noise in SCG is to reduce the pump RIN. However, since SCG pumped in the anomalous dispersion regime with picosecond or longer pulses is driven by the non-coherent process of MI, it is not evident how much would be gained from this approach [6]. To investigate this, we performed a comparative study measuring the RIN of a MIR SC generated as above, except the GSD was exchanged for a mode-locked Tm-doped fiber laser operating at 1975 nm amplified in a two-stage Tm-fiber amplifier. The mode-locked system requires a higher degree of complexity to reach stable

pulse generation, which was achieved by utilizing a semiconductor saturable absorber mirror (SESAM) within a fiber laser cavity. Compared to the GSD, this mode-locked architecture is generally more sensitive to environmental perturbations, while the gradual degradation of the SESAM presents lifetime considerations. Furthermore, it does not allow flexibility in PRR control as compared to the GSD system. This could be at least partially remedied at the expense of additional complexity, cost, and insertion loss with the inclusion of a pulse picker, although this would only allow for reducing the PRR from the free-spectral range of the mode-locked laser. This pump operated at 5.8 MHz, producing 30 ps pulses with a RIN of $< 0.11\%$ (detection limited), which is over $100\times$ lower than the GSD pump. Following a ~ 1 m section of SM1950 pulse break-up fiber, a total power of 2.09 W was launched into the same ZBLAN fiber, generating a MIR SC with 1900–3796 nm bandwidth [Fig. 5(b)] and 0.92 W output power, with 43.5% of this power above $2.4\ \mu\text{m}$. Despite the significantly lower pump RIN, the measured SC RIN was only reduced by a factor of two to three compared to the GSD pump, with values of 2.0% at 1900 nm, 9.5% at 2300 nm, and 8.5% at 3250 nm [Fig. 6(b)]. Therefore, efforts to substantially decrease the pump RIN will not be rewarded with correspondingly reduced SC RIN values, and thus for MIR SCG mode-locked sources offer only a moderate noise advantage over GSD pumping. This noise reduction should be weighed against the attractive benefits of the GSD pump, namely, a low-cost, low-complexity, and environmentally robust architecture offering simple PRR tunability and good lifetime prospects.

3. CONCLUSION

This work presents a simple and versatile scheme for MIR SCG based on an amplified 1946 nm GSD and nonlinear propagation dynamics in silica and ZBLAN fiber. Bandwidth and spectrally resolved RIN were investigated for various PRRs. The broadest spectrum was achieved at 2 MHz, with a -10 dB bandwidth of 1873–3986 nm, while the lowest RIN was achieved at 1 MHz, with values of 6.1% at 1900 nm, 10.4% at 2300 nm, and 16.6% at 3250 nm. Furthermore, a FOM quantifying the suitability of the source for maximizing application SNR demonstrated maximum performance at 3 MHz for the 3000–3500 nm spectral region. These results clearly indicate the importance of PRR control, allowing the user to optimize the SC properties to suit the requirements of the specific application. A mode-locked pump source with more than $100\times$ lower RIN and otherwise similar properties was used to generate a comparative SC spanning 1900–3796 nm. However, owing to the inherently noisy MI-based SCG process, the obtained SC RIN was only reduced by a factor of two to three compared to the GSD pump (despite the significantly lower pump noise) with values of 2.0% at 1900 nm, 9.5% at 2300 nm, and 8.5% at 3250 nm. Thus, a reduction of pump RIN does not result in a corresponding reduction in SC RIN. The advantages of the GSD-based pump are that it offers a low-cost, simple, and robust architecture with flexibility to easily adjust PRR. This should be considered when comparing performance with the mode-locked-based pump, which operates at a fixed PRR and

utilizes a SESAM, which can experience performance degradation over time and achieves pulse generation in a somewhat less environmentally robust manner.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

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